

NEWSLETTER #2

Cognitive edge-cloud with serverless computing

Welcome to the second EDGELESS Newsletter. In this issue, our goal is to furnish you with a thorough update on the progress we've made, the notable milestones we've reached

EDGELESS Offerings

Fast, not furious

Reduced tail latencies at the edge with distributed intelligence

Your application, your rules

Transparent stateless and stateful programming models

Serverless you can count on

Reliable, highly isolated, & lightweight FaaS abstractions

All for one, and one for all

Consistent QoS across the edge-cloud continuum

PROJECT Objectives

- Enable efficient data apps on dynamic edge-cloud continuum
- Enable trusted access to lambda functions on limited devices
- Develop cognitive tools for efficient edge node networks
- Define interfaces to deploy apps in multi-provider environment
- Evaluate solution in realistic heterogeneous use cases

Highlights of last 4 months

Our first scientific publication!

The paper “Blockchain-Based Services Implemented in a Microservices Architecture Using a Trusted Platform Module Applied to Electric Vehicle Charging Stations” was presented at MDPI Energies

Our Second scientific publication!

The paper “EDGELESS Project: On the Road to Serverless Edge AI” was presented a FRAME Workshop @HPDC 2023 by

EDGELESS at the Concertation and Consultation on Computing Continuum: From Cloud to Edge to IoT

The Concertation and Consultation on Computing Continuum: From Cloud to Edge to IoT event, held from October 5th to November 5th, 2023, brought together numerous industry experts, researchers, and project representatives to discuss advancements and challenges in the computing continuum.

EDGELESS First Plenary Meeting

The first plenary meeting of EDGELESS after its kick-off took place on June 5 – 6, 2023 in the beautiful city of Pisa. With the participation of 20 attendees, the event was a great opportunity for partners to come together and discuss the progress, challenges, and future directions of the EDGELESS.

Hosted by CNR-IIT, the meeting embraced a hybrid nature, allowing remote participation for those unable to attend in person.

One of the primary objectives of the plenary meeting was to review the progress made by the consortium thus far. Participants had the opportunity to present their achievements, share insights, and provide updates on their respective tasks. This comprehensive overview allowed the consortium to assess the current state of the project and identify areas where further attention and collaboration are required. Additionally, the meeting served as a platform for scheduling the next set of tasks, establishing timelines, and assigning responsibilities to ensure smooth project execution moving forward.

Advancing Efficient Serverless Computing in Heterogeneous Edge Environments with the EDGELESS Project

Serverless computing at the edge is a rapidly expanding field that has attracted significant interest due to its capacity to transform data processing and analysis.

Securing Edge Devices: The Importance of Secure Execution in the EDGELESS Project

The EDGELESS project will leverage the serverless concept in all layers of the edge-cloud continuum to enable diverse and decentralized computational resources to be available on demand, close to where data are produced or consumed.

Serverless + edge = EDGELESS

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CONSORTIUM

The project unites **12 partners** from **6 European countries**, encompassing the necessary expertise to successfully accomplish the project's ambitious goals.

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